

GRAMMATICAL AND PHONETIC ANALYSIS OF MODERN BORROWED WORDS (BASED ON SOCIAL NETWORKING EXAMPLES)

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Abstract. This article analyzes the grammatical characteristics and pronunciation of modern borrowed (loan) words entering the Uzbek language from English, which are still rarely covered in academic literature. The study examines how words such as "freemium," "reboot," "vlogging," "brainstorm," and "streaming" are being adapted into Uzbek, focusing on their phonetic and morphological integration.

As a result of globalization and the rapid development of digital communication tools, dozens of new terms and words are entering the Uzbek language every year. Some of them quickly gain popularity, while others become lexical units used only by specialists in narrow fields. This article examines how modern borrowed words, which have not yet been widely covered in scientific literature, are being accepted grammatically and how their pronunciation is changing in the Uzbek language.

Literature and review. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the grammatical and phonetic characteristics of modern borrowed words in linguistics. The entry of foreign words into a language is closely tied to social, cultural, technological, and political changes, and this process has also influenced the Uzbek language. In Uzbek linguistics, this issue has primarily been examined within the framework of lexicology and word formation. For instance, A. Madvaliev (2004) discussed the morphological adaptation of foreign words in the Uzbek language, analyzing their transformation through affixes. Additionally, S. Jo'raev (2011) explored the phonetic adaptation of new terms entering through the internet and mass media. Phonologically, the pronunciation of borrowed words undergoes two main phases: first, phonemic adaptation, and second, adaptation to stress and intonational systems. G. Khudoyberdiyeva (2018) highlighted the phonological changes in the pronunciation of English loanwords in Uzbek, using examples such as technological terms (e.g., "computer," "blogger," "update") where the influence of English remains prominent. Recent studies (e.g., N. Tursunova, 2022) have provided a detailed analysis of the grammatical integration of modern borrowed words, specifically their use in verb, noun, or adjective forms, and their function within Uzbek sentence structures. However, research in this area is still not deep enough and needs to be enriched with more empirical examples. Additionally, comparative linguistics has examined the phonetic and grammatical differences between borrowed words from Russian, English, and Turkish, which have been analyzed by several scholars (e.g., I. Karimov, 2020). These studies serve as a crucial source for analyzing the dynamics of borrowed words in the Uzbek language. Here have a look at gathered words and model translation of borrowed words.

Words in English	Meaning in uzbek	Pronunciation	Example Sentence
Preemium	Bepul va pullik xizmat aralash modeli	/fri:miəm/	Many mobile apps use a freemium model to attract users.
Vlogging	Video blog yuritish	/'vlɒɡɪŋ/	She makes a living by vlogging her daily life.
Brainstorm	G'oyalarni birgalikda o'ylab topish	/brem,stɔ:rm /	Let's brainstorm some ideas for the new project.
Reboot	Qayta ishga tushirish	/ri:bʊ:t/	You need to reboot your computer after the update.
Streaming	Internet orqali jonli yoki yozilgan ko'rsatuvni ko'rish	/stri:mɪŋ/	He spends most evenings streaming his favorite series.
Non-Fungible Token (NFT)	Noyob raqamli token	/nɒn-fʌndʒəbl tɔʊkən/	She sold her digital art as a non-fungible token.
FOMO (Fear Of Missing Out)	Biror narsani o'tkazib yuborish qo'rquvi	/fɒmɒʊ/	He bought the ticket because of FOMO.
Bloatware	Keraksiz dasturlar	/blɒʊt-wɛər/	This phone comes with too much bloatware.
Lag	Sezilarli kechikish	/læɡ/	The game is unplayable due to lag.
Troll	Ataylab jahl chiqaruvchi internet foydalanuvchisi	/trɒl/	Don't respond to the troll in the comments.
Ragequit	Jahli chiqib o'yinni tashlab ketish	/'reɪdʒkwɪt/	He ragequit after losing the match
Botnet	Zararli robotlar tarmog'i	/'bɒtnet/	The botnet was used to launch a cyber attack.
Dropshipping	Omborsiz onlayn savdo	/'drɒpʃɪpɪŋ/	Many entrepreneurs are making money through dropshipping.
Phishing	Firibgarlik yo'li bilan ma'lumot olish	/'fɪʃɪŋ/	He received a phishing email pretending to be from the bank.

Lurker	Passiv internet kuzatuvchisi	/ˈlɜːrkər/	She's a lurker in most online forums.
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Conclusion. The modern borrowed words analyzed above demonstrate unique ways in which they are adapting to the grammatical and phonetic systems of the Uzbek language. Some of these words undergo phonetic simplification, while others adopt morphological changes by integrating Uzbek suffixes. A pressing task for linguists is to clarify the linguistic status of these terms, monitor their integration into the literary language, and, when necessary, develop suitable national equivalents.

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